

LEACHING ZINC CAKES WITH SULFURIC ACID USING OZONE AS AN OXIDIZING AGENT

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Abstract. *In this article the use of ozone as an oxidizing agent for the leaching of zinc cake in sulfuric acid is investigated. Several articles about using ozone have been studied. Furthermore, the effect of acid concentration, particle size of the zinc cake, and temperature on zinc extraction efficiency were explored. The experimental findings revealed that the leaching efficiency is influenced by all of these operational factors.*

Keywords: *zinc cake, leaching, ozone, process, waste, metal extraction, solution, acid concentration, temperature.*

Introduction.

Currently, approximately 10 billion tons of minerals are mined worldwide each year. Global scientific research is focused on utilizing industrial waste as supplementary raw materials for metal production, as the volume of waste often contains greater amounts of valuable metals compared to primary ores. In this context, processing man-made waste could enable companies to significantly expand their raw material base without the need for capital investment in geological, mining, and processing operations [1].

Literature review

To date, the use of ozone for leaching zinc cakes has not been reported; however, several researchers have demonstrated its effectiveness in the oxidation of refractory sulfide ores.

Indonesian researchers explored the use of ozone as an oxidizing agent for the direct leaching of zinc sulfide (sphalerite) concentrate in a sulfuric acid medium under atmospheric pressure [2]. They investigated the effects of various factors—acid concentration, feed gas injection rate, particle size distribution, stirring speed, temperature, and slurry density—on zinc extraction efficiency. The results showed that all these parameters, except stirring speed, influenced the leaching efficiency. The study found that nearly complete zinc dissolution from the concentrate could be achieved in about seven hours under the following conditions: sulfuric acid concentration of 2 mol/l, particle size smaller than 74 μm , slurry density of 50 g/l, stirring speed of 420 rpm, feed gas injection rate of 1/min, and ambient temperature. The experimental results suggested that the dissolution reactions produced elemental sulfur that readily floated, making it easier to separate, as opposed to forming a layer on the surface of the reacted particles, which is commonly seen in systems using ferric sulfate as an oxidizing agent. This led to the conclusion that dissolved ozone plays a crucial role in enhancing the rate of zinc dissolution from the concentrate. Leaching kinetics analysis indicated that the leaching rate followed the shrinking particle model, with the overall dissolution rate of zinc being controlled by a surface reaction.

A new method for leaching zinc oxide dust using ozone oxidation in a sulfuric acid system was investigated by the authors [3]. They comprehensively studied the main factors influencing

the leaching rate, including ozone exposure time, leaching temperature, initial acidity, leaching duration, and liquid/solid mass ratio. The results indicated that the leaching efficiency is affected by all of these factors. The optimal conditions for leaching zinc and germanium from zinc oxide dust were found to be: ozone exposure time of 10 minutes, leaching temperature of 90°C, initial acidity of 160 g/l, leaching time of 60 minutes, and a liquid/solid mass ratio of 7:1. Under these optimal conditions, the leaching rates for zinc and germanium were 95.79% and 93.65%, respectively. Compared to atmospheric leaching, the ozone-assisted leaching process resulted in increases of 4.05% for zinc and 10.49% for germanium. The study concluded that ozone in the solution plays a critical role in rapidly oxidizing sulfides and releasing encapsulated germanium. The sulfuric acid-ozone system proves to be an efficient medium for extracting both zinc and germanium from zinc oxide dust.

The authors of this work [4] reported on the recycling of residue using hydrometallurgy, specifically employing sulfuric acid to leach the residue under normal pressure. In this study, the experimental conditions—including leaching temperature, leaching time, liquid/solid (L/S) mass ratio, and initial acidity—were optimized through experimental design to align with current industrial production conditions, aiming to maximize the leaching rates of zinc (Zn) and germanium (Ge). The study also analyzed the primary causes of the low leaching rate of germanium. The results indicated that the optimal reaction conditions were: initial acidity of 160 g/l, leaching temperature of 90°C, L/S mass ratio of 5:1, leaching time of 60 minutes, and stirring speed of 400 rpm. Under these conditions, the leaching rates of Zn and Ge were 83,22% and 77,29%, respectively.

The study further explored the reasons for the low leaching rates of Zn and Ge in the GCR (galvanized carbide residue) through atmospheric leaching experiments, electron probe microanalysis (EPMA), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and chemical phase analysis. The results showed that GCR mainly consists of phases such as zincite (ZnO), galena (PbS), wurtzite (ZnS), and anglesite (PbSO₄), with key elements including Zn, lead (Pb), germanium (Ge), oxygen (O), sulfur (S), silicon (Si), aluminum (Al), and iron (Fe). This research provides valuable insights for researchers and serves as a reference for large-scale recycling of zinc and germanium resources in the future.

This article [5] discusses the use of an Ultrasound–Ozone Integrated Approach to enhance the leaching of copper (Cu) from the printed circuit boards of discarded mobile phones. The recovery of metals from electronic waste, particularly mobile phones, is of growing interest due to both environmental and economic benefits. The study presents a simple and effective method for leaching copper from these circuit boards by combining ultrasound and ozone treatments. Solid phases were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), while inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) was employed to measure the metal concentrations in the liquid phases. The study investigated the effects of several key parameters on leaching efficiency, including ultrasound power, ozone dosage, hydrochloric acid (HCl) concentration, liquid/solid ratio, temperature, and reaction time. The results revealed that the optimal conditions for copper leaching were: an ozone dose of 700 mg/h, HCl concentration of 3.0 M, liquid/solid ratio of 8, and a temperature of 333 K. Under these conditions, approximately 99% of the copper was leached after 180 minutes. The leaching kinetics were analyzed using the shrinking core model, which indicated that the process

is governed by a surface chemical reaction. The activation energy of the leaching reaction, calculated using the Two-Point form of the Arrhenius equation, was found to be 10,852 kJ/mol.

The article [6] has reported improvements in gold cyanidation from refractory concentrates through pre-oxidation using ozone, demonstrating its effectiveness in unlocking gold from sulfide minerals, particularly pyrite and arsenopyrite. Ozone, with a reduction potential of 2.07 V, is more powerful than other oxidants such as persulfate (2.01 V) and hydrogen peroxide (1.77 V). One advantage of using ozone is that it does not introduce new ions into the system, which could potentially cause downstream issues. For example, nitrates, if introduced, could be reduced at the cathode during the zinc electrowinning process, leading to a reduction in current efficiency.

The authors [7,8] have been studied the process of leaching zinc cake with sulfuric acid under different conditions. Based on the results of the experimental work, graphs of the interdependence of various parameters were drawn up. In the end optimal conditions for washing zinc cake in sulfuric acid were selected.

Therefore, in the present study, the use of ozone for the direct leaching of Zn cake with sulfuric acid was explored, given ozone's potential as a promising alternative oxidant, and the mechanism of the leaching in the system is elucidated.

Materials and methods

A sample of zinc cake from the Zinc Plant of JSC "Almalyk MMC" was analyzed and found to have the following chemical composition (in %): Zn_{tot} -20,79; Zn_w -5,58; Zn_a -12,87; S_{tot} -7,87; S_{SO_4} -6,52; Pb-6,89; Fe-11,24; SiO_2 -8,42; Al_2O_3 -1,44; Cu-1,78; Cd-0,23; CaO-2,67; MnO-0,8. The primary chemical compounds present in the zinc cake include sphalerite, zinc ferrite, copper ferrite, metal silicates, copper sulfate, zinc sulfate, gypsum, and lead sulfate.

To investigate the process of agitation of high-temperature leaching of zinc cake, a specialized setup consisting of a flask heater and a mechanical stirrer was employed. The experiments were conducted as follows: the zinc cake was first crushed into particle sizes ranging from -0,1 to 10 mm.

The crushed zinc cake was then placed in the leaching apparatus, and a solution of sulfuric acid and ozone was added. The mixture was heated and maintained at the desired temperature for a specified duration. The temperature was precisely controlled using a microprocessor-based automatic controller.

Results and discussions.

In this study, the effects of acid concentration, ozone injection rate, particle size, and temperature on zinc dissolution efficiency were investigated. Based on the experimental results, a potential leaching mechanism was proposed.

Effect of particle size. The experiments were carried out as follows: the fraction of zinc cake <0.1 mm and +1 to -10 mm was taken. The crushed zinc cake sample was placed in a leaching unit, a sulfuric acid solution was added, heated and kept for a certain time. The temperature was controlled through a microprocessor automatic controller.

The study of the effect of the duration of the process on the leaching of zinc from the cake with a sulfuric acid solution with a concentration of 120–200 g/l at different temperatures and two classes of particle sizes shows that in the initial period (up to 60–90 min) the transition of zinc into the solution proceeds very intensively, and after 3-5 hours, the dynamic equilibrium of the leaching process is established (Fig. 1-2).

Fig. 1. Dependence of zinc solubility versus initial acid concentration and particle size (-0.1 mm) at various temperatures.

Fig. 2. Dependence of zinc solubility versus initial acid concentration and particle size (+0.1-10 mm) at various temperatures.

Effect of temperature. A series of experiments was carried out to evaluate the effect of acid concentration on zinc dissolution efficiency by varying the sulfuric acid concentration in the range of 120 to 200 g/l at different temperatures and with ozone. The results, summarized in Fig. 3, demonstrate that the presence of acid is clearly important in the leaching process, as the zinc extraction rate increased with increasing sulfuric acid concentration and high temperature.

Effect of Acid Concentration and ozone. A series of experiments were conducted to evaluate how the sulfuric acid concentration influences zinc dissolution efficiency. The sulfuric acid concentration was varied between 120 and 200 g/l, and the leaching was carried out at temperatures ranging from 70 to 80°C. The experiment results that with and without ozone have been shown in Fig. 4, clearly indicate that the presence of acid and ozone plays a crucial role in the leaching process. As the sulfuric acid concentration increased, the zinc extraction rate also increased, but this effect was observed only up to a concentration of 180 g/l. Beyond this concentration, further increases in acid concentration did not lead to a significant improvement in zinc dissolution efficiency.

Fig. 3. Dependence of zinc solubility versus initial acid concentration and particle size -1 mm at various temperatures and with ozone.

Fig.4. Dependence of zinc solubility versus initial acid concentration and ozone. Bars: 1- experiments without ozone; 2- experiments with ozone.

Experiments were conducted using ozone consumption rate of 3000 ml/h and varying concentrations of sulfuric acid. The HY-002-3A model ozone generator was utilized for the ozone supply during the experiments. The results of these experiments are presented in table 1.

Table 1
Results of experiments on high-temperature leaching of zinc cake by ozone, solution and cake composition

Elements	Content in the initial cake, %	Extraction into solution, %	Composition of the solution, g/l	Content in the leaching cake, %
Zn	20,79	94,7	62,32	3,27
Pb	6,89	1,5	0,31	16,8
Cu	1,78	93,22	5,32	0,32

Conclusion.

In conclusion, we can say that the high-temperature sulfuric acid leaching with ozone has proven itself well in the processing of zinc cake, providing selectivity and complexity of processing. The optimal duration of leaching is 4 hours with ozone and a sulfuric acid concentration of 180 g/l, and a leaching temperature of 70-80°C. The extraction of zinc into the

solution in this case is 90-95%, copper 90-94% with a cake yield of 35-45%. The resulting sulfuric acid solution contains (g/l): zinc – 62,32; copper -5,32; lead – 0,31. The concentration of zinc in the solution is sufficient for the electrolysis of zinc.

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